

1 **The association between spirometry measurement quality,**
2 **cognitive function, and mortality**

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20

21 **Abstract**

22 **Background:** Population studies that assess lung function usually exclude results of individuals
23 with poor-quality measurements, which often means excluding many subjects. Impaired
24 cognition is frequently associated with poor-quality spirometry; excluding such subjects may
25 introduce a selection bias in studies with lung function as either outcome or exposure. We
26 investigated the association between poor-quality spirometry and impaired cognitive function
27 and whether poor-quality spirometry is associated with future mortality risk independently from
28 cognitive function.

29 **Methods:** We used data from a prospective cohort in three Central and Eastern European
30 countries; 12,087 individuals aged 45-75 years (54% females) with complete information on
31 variables of interest were included. Standard memory, verbal fluency, and executive cognitive
32 domain tests were converted into latent variable z-scores and divided into quartiles. Spirometry
33 tests were classified into two categories based on repeatability criteria: good- (71%) vs. poor-
34 quality spirometry (29% of participants). Those with good-quality spirometry were further
35 classified, using forced vital capacity (FVC) and forced expiratory volume in the first second
36 (FEV₁), as healthy spirometry (62%) or impaired spirometry (9%). Multinomial logistic regression
37 was used to assess the association between poor-quality spirometry and cognitive function,
38 and a Cox proportional regression was used to analyze the risk of total mortality over a 17-year
39 follow-up.

40 **Results:** After controlling for a range of covariates, lower cognitive function predicted lower
41 quality spirometry. In the highest cognitive function quartile, compared with the lowest quartile,
42 the odds ratios of poor-quality spirometry and impaired lung function were 0.82 (95%CI: 0.72-
43 0.92) and 0.64 (0.52-0.78), respectively. Impaired spirometry was associated with higher
44 mortality risk even after adjusting for cognition (adjusted hazard ratio: 1.61, 95%CI: 1.44-1.79),
45 but mortality risk was similar in subjects with poor vs. good quality, HR 1.02 (0.93-1.10)

46 **Conclusion:** Higher cognitive function was associated with a lower risk of poor-quality
47 spirometry. However, the lack of independent association of poor-quality spirometry with
48 mortality suggests that excluding poor-quality spirometry measurements from analyses is
49 unlikely to introduce a major bias.

50 **Keywords:** aging, mortality, cognition, lung function, quality of spirometry.

51 **Contributions to the literature**

52 There is good evidence that lung function and cognition are positively associated, and both
53 these markers are prospectively associated with mortality.

54 Subjects with lower cognitive functions are more likely to provide low quality spirometry data.

55 Excluding poor-quality spirometry data is unlikely to introduce major bias in estimating mortality
56 risk.

57 **Background**

58 Spirometry is a well-established (and often overlooked) biomarker of health and future risk [1,2].

59 However, the measurement is not always performed correctly. Poor-quality spirometry is

60 defined as the inability of people to perform a respiratory test that fulfills the acceptability and

61 repeatability criteria [3]. During a spirometry examination, individuals first receive a series of

62 instructions on how to perform the test. Two correctly performed readings are needed to

63 evaluate the pulmonary capacity; however, individuals must repeat the test three to eight times

64 to meet acceptability and repeatability criteria [3]. Around 10% of people are usually not able to

65 reach these standards [4], and the information on their pulmonary capacity remains unreliable.

66 This may potentially introduce a selection bias if results from spirometry that failed to satisfy

67 acceptability and repeatability criteria are excluded from statistical analyses.

68 A spirometry test requires a comfortable environment, a well-trained technician, and the ability

69 of the person to understand and execute a list of instructions. Previous studies report that older

70 people with compromised cognition may be unable to perform good-quality spirometry [5–9].
71 However, another study found that after controlling for covariates, an impaired MMSE (Mini-
72 Mental State Exam) was not an independent predictor of poor-quality spirometry [10].
73 Additionally, as people age, the number of comorbidities is likely to increase, which can also
74 lead to poor spirometry performance.

75 Several other risk factors might explain the association between cognitive function and poor-
76 quality spirometry, although the results tend to be inconsistent. Females and younger
77 individuals have higher odds of having good-quality spirometry while education did not seem to
78 play a role [11]. In the United States people with lower income, males, and African Americans
79 were more likely to demonstrate good-quality spirometry measurement [12]. Bellia et al. [9]
80 found that motor and sensory deficits, depression, dementia, and malnutrition are associated
81 with poor-quality spirometry in subjects older than 65 years.

82 In addition to the association between cognition and poor-quality spirometry, there is evidence
83 that cognitive function is also associated with impaired lung function [13,14]. As most studies
84 of poor-quality spirometry compared poor-quality with good-quality spirometry, which includes
85 both healthy and impaired lung function, the comparison may not be perfect.

86 Nevertheless, there is no evidence whether poor-quality spirometry is associated with future
87 health outcomes, while there is extensive evidence that low cognitive function [15,16] and
88 impaired lung function [17] are associated with a higher risk of mortality.

89 In this study, we investigated the associations between cognitive function and poor-quality
90 spirometry, and whether poor-quality spirometry is associated with future mortality both before
91 and after controlling for cognitive function.

92 **Methods**

93 *Study sample*

94 The HAPIEE study (Health, Alcohol, and Psychosocial Factors in Eastern Europe) [18] is a
95 population-based epidemiological study carried out in urban centers of Poland, Lithuania, and
96 the Czech Republic. The study was approved by the Ethics Committees at University College
97 London, UK, and in each participating center. The first wave was collected between 2002 and
98 2008. It included health questionnaires and medical examinations of 26,746 adults aged 44 to
99 75. From these, 11,766 individuals were not invited to the cognitive function examination and
100 therefore were excluded as ineligible from the final sample (Figure 1). Out of the remained
101 people, 2,589 did not participate in the lung function testing. Additionally, 101 individuals did
102 not provide consent to check the mortality status in the death registry. A smaller number of
103 individuals did not record information on body mass index (BMI), smoking status, level of
104 education, or previous diagnosis/hospitalization due to stroke or respiratory disease (5, 43, 9,
105 121, and 25 individuals, respectively). The analytical sample was restricted to individuals with
106 complete (non-missing) information on spirometry, cognition, mortality, and covariates
107 (n=12,087).

108

109 **Figure 1.** Participants of the HAPIEE study excluded from the analysis.

110 *Spirometry*

111 The lung function was assessed using a Micro-Medical Microplus spirometer at the examination
 112 center by trained personnel. All participants performed at least three maneuvers following the
 113 criteria of the American Thoracic Society (ATS) and the European Respiratory Society (ERS) [3].

114 Examiners visually inspected the spirograms to achieve an expiration longer than 6 seconds and
 115 a good peak expiratory flow with no cough during the first second of the test. Repeatability

116 criteria were used to classify results into good-quality or poor-quality spirometry. Repeatability

117 refers to the difference between the two highest values of the forced vital capacity (FVC) and the

118 two highest values of forced expiratory volume in the first second (FEV₁). The difference must be
119 lower than 150 ml to fulfill the criteria [3]. Spirometry results were classified as poor-quality if
120 patients failed the repeatability criteria in either FVC or FEV₁, otherwise, the test was considered
121 as good quality (Figure 2).

122
123 **Figure 2.** Flowchart illustrating the classification process for spirometry results into specific
124 categories.

125 Individuals with good-quality spirometry were further categorized as healthy or impaired
126 spirometry based on the algorithm proposed by Pellegrino et al. [19] for the interpretation of
127 spirometry (Figure 2). Participants were categorized as healthy spirometry when achieved
128 FEV₁/FVC ratio and FVC higher than the lower limits of normality (LLN), otherwise, it was
129 considered impaired spirometry. The LLN for the FEV₁/FVC ratio and FVC represent the lower
130 fifth percentile of the reference values, which are specific for every individual based on their
131 age, sex, and height. The LLN formulas were published by Kuster et al. [20] and are adjusted and
132 specific for the Caucasian population.

133 *Cognitive function*

134 Cognitive function was tested using three standard tasks that evaluated different aspects of
135 cognition. *Immediate and delayed verbal memory* consisted of a list of 10 words listened to by
136 the participant and immediately asked them to remember as many words as possible in two
137 minutes. The task was repeated three times and recorded in a range from zero to ten depending
138 on the number of correct words. After five minutes the participants were asked again to recall as
139 many words as possible. In the meantime, *semantic and verbal fluency* was evaluated asking
140 the participants to name as many animals as possible in one minute. Then, *speed and*
141 *concentration* were tested using a sheet with random letters of the alphabet in which
142 participants had to cross out letters P and W.

143 The scores of each cognitive test were standardized to the respective z-scores to give a mean of
144 zero and a standard deviation of one. The six z-scores were used to predict a latent variable
145 called “Cognition” where higher scores represent better cognitive function. First, we checked
146 the Spearman correlations of the six cognitive tests [see Additional file 1]. Second, we
147 employed latent class analysis to calculate the latent variable “Cognition” and extracted the
148 predicted factor. Finally, we categorized the predicted factor into quartiles (4).

149 *Mortality*

150 Individuals were followed until August 2017 in Poland, April 2019 in Lithuania, and January
151 2021 in the Czech Republic. Dates of deaths were obtained from the national death registry. All-
152 cause mortality was used in the analyses.

153 *Covariates*

154 From the health questionnaires, we used a set of covariates that have been previously
155 associated with worst pulmonary outcomes and mortality [21,22]: age, sex, smoking,
156 education, diagnosed or hospitalized for stroke, and diagnosed or hospitalized for respiratory
157 disease. Smoking was recoded as a dummy variable between those who never smoked (0) and

158 past and current smokers (1). The highest level of education accomplished was divided into
159 three categories: no education plus primary education (0), secondary education (1), and tertiary
160 education (2). If a person was previously diagnosed or hospitalized for stroke was coded as one
161 (1), otherwise zero (0). Identical coding was used if diagnosed or hospitalized for respiratory
162 disease. The BMI is a derived variable using the conventional formula $\text{weight}(\text{kg})/\text{height}(\text{m})^2$.

163 *Statistical analysis*

164 Analyses were conducted using Stata/IC 16.1. First, we performed multinomial logistic
165 regression to investigate the associations between cognitive function and the categories of
166 healthy, impaired, and poor-quality spirometry, with healthy spirometry as the reference group.
167 In model 1, cognitive function was adjusted for age and sex, and in model 2 cognitive function
168 was additionally adjusted for a range of covariates. Results are presented as odds ratios (OR)
169 and 95% confidence intervals (CI). Second, we used logistic regression to analyze associations
170 of cognitive function with good- vs. poor-quality spirometry measurement.

171 Third, we calculated mortality rates (deaths per 1000 person-years) for each spirometry
172 category. We used Cox proportional hazards regression models to assess the association
173 between spirometry categories and all-cause mortality and estimate hazard ratios (HRs) at 95%
174 CI. Three models were constructed: model 1 was adjusted for age and sex; Model 2 was
175 adjusted for age, sex, and cognitive function as a continuous variable, and Model 3 was
176 adjusted for all covariates including cognitive function as a continuous variable. Cox regression
177 analyses were also performed for the association of mortality with good- vs. poor-quality
178 spirometry measurement.

179 **Results**

180 The characteristics of participants are presented in Table 1. Age, sex, BMI, smoking status,
181 education, history of stroke, history of respiratory disease, mortality, and cognitive function

182 were classified into three spirometry categories: healthy, impaired, and poor-quality spirometry.
 183 The analytical sample included 12,087 individuals, of whom 29% had poor-quality spirometry
 184 and 54% were females. The last day of follow-up was the 30th of January 2021. In total, 2,598
 185 (21.49%) individuals died during this time.

186 The category of impaired spirometry had the highest prevalence of smoking (61%), primary
 187 education (21%), previous diagnosis or hospitalization for stroke (6%), previous diagnosis or
 188 hospitalization for respiratory diseases (28%), and mortality (38%). By contrast, most people
 189 with healthy spirometry are in the highest quartile of cognitive function (30%), while most
 190 people with impaired spirometry (30%) are in the lowest quartile of cognitive function.

191 **Table 1.** Characteristics of participants of the HAPIEE study separated into categories: healthy,
 192 impaired, and poor-quality spirometry.

	Good-Quality spirometry				Poor-Quality spirometry	
	Healthy spirometry n=7 457 (62%)		Impaired spirometry n=1 149 (9%)		n=3 481 (29%)	
	N	%	N	%	N	%
Sex						
Males	3 197	42.87	595	51.78	1 794	51.54
Females	4 260	57.13	554	48.22	1 687	48.46
Age, years, mean, SD	61.16	7.02	62.74	6.25	61.84	6.91
BMI, kg/m², mean, SD	28.93	4.85	29.80	5.68	29.23	5.16
Smoking						
Never	4 334	58.12	452	39.34	1 962	56.36
Past or current smoker	3 123	41.88	697	60.66	1 519	43.64
Education						
Primary	848	11.37	236	20.54	487	13.99
Secondary or Vocational	3 506	47.02	605	52.65	1 640	47.11
Tertiary	3 103	41.61	308	26.81	1 354	38.90
Hospitalized or diagnosed for stroke						
No	7 219	96.81	1 084	94.34	3 321	95.40
Yes	238	3.19	65	5.66	160	4.60
Hospitalized or diagnosed for Chronic respiratory disease						

No	6 401	85.84	831	72.32	2 954	84.86
Yes	1 056	14.16	318	27.68	527	15.14
Mortality						
No	6 101	81.82	714	62.14	2 674	76.82
Yes	1 356	18.18	435	37.86	807	23.18
Cognitive function						
Cognition factor, mean, SD	0.11	0.64	-0.12	0.69	-0.002	0.67
First quartile	1 387	18.60	346	30.11	835	23.99
Second quartile	1 696	22.74	312	27.15	915	26.29
Third quartile	2 100	28.16	257	22.37	844	24.25
Fourth quartile	2 274	30.49	234	20.37	887	25.48

193

194 Table 2 shows the OR from the multinomial logistic regression model, where the outcome
195 variable is spirometry with three categories. In the age-sex adjusted model, higher cognitive
196 function predicted lower odds of being in the impaired (OR: 0.50, 95%CI: 0.41-0.60) and poor-
197 quality (0.73, 0.64-0.82) spirometry categories compared to healthy spirometry. Similarly, there
198 was a strong association of cognitive function with poor- (vs. good) quality spirometry
199 measurement; the highest quartile of cognitive function was associated with lower odds of
200 poor-quality spirometry (0.81, 0.71-0.91). Additional adjustments for other covariates (model 2)
201 somewhat reduced these estimates but both remained strong and statistically significant. Aside
202 from cognitive function, we found that being female was associated with a lower risk of poor-
203 quality spirometry, while previous diagnosis or hospitalization for stroke increased the risk of
204 poor-quality spirometry [see Additional file 2].

205 **Table 2.** Odds ratios of impaired vs. healthy spirometry, poor-quality vs. healthy spirometry, poor-
206 vs. good-quality spirometry,

	Cognitive function Model 1, OR (95% CI)				Cognitive function Model 2, OR (95% CI)			
	First quartile	Second quartile	Third quartile	Fourth quartile	First quartile	Second quartile	Third quartile	Fourth quartile
Multinomial regression (healthy spirometry is the reference group)								

Impaired vs. healthy spirometry	Ref.	0.78 (0.66 – 0.92)	0.55 (0.45 – 0.65)	0.50 (0.41 – 0.60)	Ref.	0.87 (0.73 – 1.04)	0.65 (0.54 – 0.78)	0.64 (0.52 – 0.78)
Poor-quality vs. healthy spirometry	Ref.	0.93 (0.82 – 1.04)	0.72 (0.63 – 0.81)	0.73 (0.64 – 0.82)	Ref.	0.95 (0.84 – 1.07)	0.74 (0.65 – 0.84)	0.77 (0.67 – 0.87)
Logistic regression (good-quality spirometry is the reference group)								
Poor- vs. good-quality spirometry	Ref.	0.97 (0.86 – 1.09)	0.79 (0.70 – 0.88)	0.81 (0.71 – 0.91)	Ref.	0.96 (0.86 – 1.09)	0.79 (0.70 – 0.89)	0.82 (0.72 – 0.92)
Model 1 adjusted for age and sex Model 2 adjusted for age, sex, BMI, smoking status, education, hospitalized or diagnosed for respiratory disease, hospitalized or diagnosed for stroke.								

207

208 Table 3 shows the hazard ratios (HR) of mortality between categories of spirometry. In total,
 209 2,598 individuals died during the follow-up. The mortality rate per 1000 person-years was the
 210 lowest among subjects with healthy spirometry, and highest among people with impaired
 211 spirometry. The Cox proportional hazard regression showed that, compared to the healthy
 212 spirometry group, poor-quality spirometry was associated with HR 1.18 when controlled for age
 213 and sex, which was attenuated to 1.15 when additionally adjusted for cognitive function, and to
 214 1.12 in the fully adjusted model. When using the dichotomous variable of the quality of
 215 spirometry, poor-quality spirometry itself did not predict future mortality, either before (HR 1.03,
 216 CI 0.94-1.12) or after adjustment (HR 1.02, CI: 0.93-1.10).

217 **Table 3.** Association between spirometry categories and all-cause mortality using Cox
 218 regression analysis.

	No. of persons	No. of deaths	Person years of follow-up	Deaths per 1000 person-years	Model 1 HR (95% CI)	Model 2 HR (95% CI)	Model 3 HR (95% CI)

Three categories of spirometry							
Healthy spirometry	7 457	1 356	93 613	14.48 (13.73 – 15.27)	1.00	1.00	1.00
Impaired spirometry	1 149	434	13 346	32.51 (29.59 – 35.72)	1.99 (1.78 – 2.22)	1.89 (1.69 – 2.10)	1.61 (1.44 – 1.79)
Poor-quality spirometry	3 481	806	42 908	18.78 (17.53 – 20.12)	1.18 (1.07 – 1.28)	1.15 (1.04 – 1.25)	1.12 (1.02 – 1.22)
Two categories of spirometry							
Good-quality spirometry	8 606	1 791	106 959	16.73 (15.97 – 17.52)	1.00	1.00	1.00
Poor-quality spirometry	3 481	807	42 908	18.78 (17.53 – 20.12)	1.03 (0.94 – 1.12)	1.01 (0.93 – 1.09)	1.02 (0.93 – 1.10)
<p>Model 1 adjusted for age and sex.</p> <p>Model 2 adjusted for age, sex, and cognitive function.</p> <p>Model 3 adjusted for age, sex, BMI, smoking status, education, hospitalized or diagnosed for respiratory disease, hospitalized or diagnosed for stroke, and cognitive function.</p>							

219

220 In a sensitivity analysis [see Additional file 3] we reviewed the criteria for the classification of
221 quality of spirometry. Individuals previously classified as poor-quality spirometry (they did not
222 meet repeatability criteria between the two highest values of FVC and FEV₁), but that met
223 repeatability criteria between the second highest and the third highest value of FEV₁ and FVC
224 were considered with good quality, and therefore, reassigned into healthy and impaired
225 spirometry categories. This reclassification did not substantially change the results [see
226 Additional files 4 and 5]. Additionally, we tested the robustness of cognitive function using the
227 full sample size [see Additional file 6], which showed identical results to Table 2. Finally, the
228 composite score of cognitive function showed stronger power than individual domains of
229 cognition [see Additional file 7].

230 **Discussion**

231 This study investigated the relationship between cognitive function and poor-quality spirometry
232 tests, as well as the potential association of poor-quality spirometry tests with future mortality.

233 The motivation for these analyses was two-fold. First, to confirm whether lower cognition is
234 associated with a higher likelihood of poor-quality spirometry. Second, to see whether this
235 association, if it exists, may introduce a selection bias in analyses of lung functions with
236 mortality outcomes if subjects who provided poor-quality spirometry measurements are
237 excluded from the analyses. We found that cognitive function was significantly inversely
238 associated with the likelihood of having impaired or poor-quality spirometry. However, the
239 longitudinal association of poor-quality spirometry with mortality was weak (or non-existent)
240 and it was not materially attenuated by adjustment for cognitive function. At least in this cohort
241 study, excluding “poor-quality” spirometry from analyses did not seem to lead to a major bias in
242 analyses of all-cause mortality.

243 The results on associations of spirometry with both cognition and future mortality risks were as
244 expected and consistent with the previous body of evidence [1,13,14,16,23,24]. However,
245 despite the simultaneous association between the quality of spirometry measurement and
246 cognition and between cognition and mortality, there was no detectable association between
247 poor-quality spirometry measurement and mortality. This observation suggests that the
248 strength of the association of cognition with poor-quality measurement is too weak to translate
249 into an association of poor-quality measurement with mortality. Results may look differently for
250 health outcomes other than mortality, but our data suggest that excluding poor-quality
251 measurements from analyses is unlikely to produce a major selection bias that would change
252 the effect estimates for spirometry.

253 Our findings align with some of the existing evidence. Previous studies have reported that older
254 people with compromised cognitive function may struggle to perform good-quality spirometry

255 [5-7]. However, some studies found no association associations between poor-quality
256 spirometry and cognition [10]. Inconsistencies might arise from differences in the sample
257 characteristics composition, measurements of cognitive function, and available information to
258 evaluate the quality of spirometry. For instance, our study's mean age was 62, while in other
259 studies the mean age was 73 to 75 [6,8,9] and 84 [7,10], which are more likely to have a higher
260 prevalence of cognitive deficits and therefore fail the test; however, Haynes [25] found that
261 individuals older than 80 years had similar quality of spirometry compared to individuals aged
262 40 to 50. Turkeshi et al. [10] included spirograms to classify the quality of spirometry into four
263 categories, but spirograms were not available in our dataset for a secondary analysis. Finally,
264 some authors used separate domains of cognition instead of a composite score. When specific
265 cognitive domains were tested, such as the executive function assessed by the MMSE,
266 the findings were negative [7]. Our results suggest that cognitive function remains a significant
267 predictor when using a composite score derived from testing multiple domains [See Additional
268 file 7].

269 In addition to differences in cognitive assessment methods, differences in statistical modeling
270 approaches or differences in comparison groups and classification of healthy and impaired
271 spirometry may play a role in the inconsistencies in previous studies. Our study sample was
272 younger than many samples previously explored; while this confirms that lower cognitive
273 function could predict poor-quality spirometry, differences in age groups between studies may
274 also affect the consistency of results. Similar to other studies, we found that age was not a
275 determinant of poor-quality spirometry [25]. Previous research has also identified various
276 sociodemographic factors associated with spirometry performance [11,12]. Our findings
277 corroborate that females are less likely to have poor-quality spirometry, while education
278 showed no detectable effect.

279 One issue to consider is the very high proportion (29%) of subjects classified as providing poor-
280 quality spirometry measurement. This is much higher than the 10% reported by many previous
281 studies [4], but parallel to the 25% reported by Queiroz and colleagues [6]. One study made in
282 Poland found that 3.5% of subjects fail to achieve repeatability criteria in FVC and 13.6% in FEV₁
283 [26]. Another group in Italy [9] found that, in healthy individuals, 4.2% failed to get reproducible
284 FEV₁ and 9% failed to get reproducible FVC, however, they used a cut-off of 200ml instead of the
285 150ml we used. In our population-based sample, we found that the percentage of failure was
286 15.7% for FEV₁ and 22% for FVC. It is not clear what may be the reason, as measurements were
287 made by trained personnel in a controlled environment in clinics. A small variation of the
288 spirometry estimates can be explained by the quality of the spirometry device. A study of 34
289 patients found that 2% of the variation in spirometry measurements was dependent on small
290 flow-sensing devices versus volume-sensing spirometers [27]. In addition, technicians play a
291 critical role in obtaining good-quality spirometry [28], however, we were unable to include this
292 variable because this information was not available in our data.

293 Several other limitations should be considered. First, although we adjusted for many covariates,
294 unmeasured confounders may still influence the observed associations. Second, the cognitive
295 assessments used in this study may not fully capture all dimensions of cognition, possibly
296 leading to an underestimation of the relationship between cognitive function and spirometry
297 quality. We suggest that the association between cognitive function and poor-quality spirometry
298 needs more research, mainly including more domains of cognitive function. Finally, the utility of
299 poor-quality spirometry as a biomarker of earlier mortality is uncertain and should be confirmed
300 or refuted in other populations.

301 **Conclusions**

302 In conclusion, our study suggests that lower cognitive function is associated with both worse
303 lung function (impaired spirometry) and poor-quality spirometry. While our results do not

304 provide evidence that excluding poor-quality spirometry may not introduce a major bias from
305 analyses of mortality, the association between cognitive function and the ability to correctly
306 complete spirometry may still affect studies of respiratory functions. These findings underscore
307 the need for robust spirometry testing protocols that would minimize the proportion of low-
308 quality measurements. Further studies should explore poor-quality spirometry testing, as it
309 might be an indicator of impaired cognitive function and may potentially predict earlier
310 mortality.

311 **List of abbreviations:**

312 BMI Body mass index

313 CI Confidence interval

314 FEV₁ Forced expiratory volume in the first second

315 FVC Forced vital capacity

316 HR Hazard ratio

317 LLN Lower limit of normality

318 MMSE Mini Mental State exam

319 OR Odds ratio

320 **Declarations:**

321 **Ethics approval and consent to participate**

322 This study involves human participants and was approved by the University College London, UK,
323 and by the local ethics committee in every participating center. Participants gave informed
324 consent to participate in the study before taking part. The study protocols were approved by
325 ethical committees at University College London, UK, and at each participating center.

326 **Consent for publication**

327 Not applicable.

328 **Availability of data and materials**

329 Data are available upon reasonable request.

330 **Competing interests**

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344 **Authors' contributions**

345 CQ-H, HP, and MB (guarantors of the paper) co-designed the paper. Material preparation and
346 data collection were performed by MK, AT, NC, MB, and HP. Data analyses were performed by
347 CQ-H, TC, MB, and HP. The first draft of the manuscript was written by CQ-H, and all authors

348 commented on previous versions of the manuscript. All authors read and approved the final
349 manuscript.

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355 **References**

- 356 1. Wan ES, Balte P, Schwartz JE, Bhatt SP, Cassano PA, Couper D, et al. Association
357 between Preserved Ratio Impaired Spirometry and Clinical Outcomes in US Adults.
358 JAMA. 2021 Dec 14;326(22):2287–98.
- 359 2. Agusti A, Fabbri LM, Baraldi E, Celli B, Corradi M, Faner R, et al. Spirometry: A practical
360 lifespan predictor of global health and chronic respiratory and non-respiratory diseases.
361 Eur J Intern Med. 2021 Jul 1;89:3–9.
- 362 3. Graham BL, Steenbruggen I, Barjaktarevic IZ, Cooper BG, Hall GL, Hallstrand TS, et al.
363 Standardization of spirometry 2019 update an official American Thoracic Society and
364 European Respiratory Society technical statement. Am J Respir Crit Care Med. 2019 Oct
365 15;200(8):E70–88.
- 366 4. Berresheim H, Beine A, van Kampen V, Lehnert M, Nöllenheidt C, Brüning T, et al. ATS/
367 ERS spirometry quality criteria in real life. Results of two occupational field studies.
368 Respir Physiol Neurobiol. 2023 Sep 1;315.
- 369 5. Allen S, Yeung P, Janczewski M, Siddique N. Predicting inadequate spirometry technique
370 and the use of FEV1/FEV3 as an alternative to FEV1/FVC for patients with mild cognitive
371 impairment. Clin Respir J. 2008;2(4):208–13.
- 372 6. de Queiroz RS, de Almeida Faria LM, Oliveira Carneiro JA, Coqueiro R da S, Fernandes
373 MH. Age and mini-mental state examination score can predict poor-quality spirometry in
374 the elderly: A cross-sectional study. Clinics. 2018;73.
- 375 7. Allen SC, Baxter M. A comparison of four tests of cognition as predictors of inability to
376 perform spirometry in old age. Age Ageing. 2009;38(5):537–41.
- 377 8. Sherman CB, Kern D, Richardson ER, Hubert M, Fogel BS. Cognitive Function and
378 Spirometry Performance in the Elderly. American Review of Respiratory Disease.
379 1993;148(1):123–6.

- 380 9. Bellia V, Pistelli R, Catalano F, Antonelli-Incalzi R, Grassi V, Melillo G, et al. Quality
381 Control of Spirometry in the Elderly. The SA.R.A. Study. *Am J Respir Crit Care Med*
382 [Internet]. 2000;161:1094–100. Available from: www.atsjournals.org
- 383 10. Turkeshi E, Zelenukha D, Vaes B, Andreeva E, Frolova E, Degryse JM. Predictors of poor-
384 quality spirometry in two cohorts of older adults in Russia and Belgium: A cross-sectional
385 study. *NPJ Prim Care Respir Med*. 2015 Jul 23;25.
- 386 11. Tan WC, Bourbeau J, O'donnell D, Aaron S, Maltais F, Marciniuk D, et al. Quality
387 assurance of spirometry in a population-based study-predictors of good outcome in
388 spirometry testing. *COPD: Journal of Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease*.
389 2014;11(2):143–51.
- 390 12. Lawrence KG, Jackson WB, Ramsey S, Kwok RK, Engel LS, Curry MD, et al. Spirometry
391 quality predictors in a large multistate prospective study. *Respir Med*. 2021 Nov 1;188.
- 392 13. Dodd JW. Lung disease as a determinant of cognitive decline and dementia. Vol. 7,
393 *Alzheimer's Research and Therapy*. BioMed Central Ltd.; 2015.
- 394 14. Qiao H, Chen M, Li S, Li Y, Sun Y, Wu Y. Poor lung function accelerates cognitive decline in
395 middle-aged and older adults: Evidence from the English Longitudinal Study of Ageing.
396 *Arch Gerontol Geriatr*. 2020 Sep 1;90.
- 397 15. St John PD, Tyas SL, Griffith LE, Menec V. The cumulative effect of frailty and cognition on
398 mortality - Results of a prospective cohort study. *Int Psychogeriatr*. 2017 Apr 1;29(4):535–
399 42.
- 400 16. Tsui A, Searle SD, Bowden H, Hoffmann K, Hornby J, Goslett A, et al. The effect of
401 baseline cognition and delirium on long-term cognitive impairment and mortality: a
402 prospective population-based study. *Lancet Healthy Longev*. 2022 Apr 1;3(4):e232–41.
- 403 17. Weinmayr G, Schulz H, Klenk J, Denkinger M, Duran-Tauleria E, Koenig W, et al.
404 Association of lung function with overall mortality is independent of inflammatory,
405 cardiac, and functional biomarkers in older adults: the ActiFE-study. *Sci Rep*. 2020 Dec
406 1;10(1).
- 407 18. Peasey A, Bobak M, Kubinova R, Malyutina S, Pajak A, Tamosiunas A, et al. Determinants
408 of cardiovascular disease and other non-communicable diseases in Central and Eastern
409 Europe: Rationale and design of the HAPIEE study. *BMC Public Health* [Internet]. 2006
410 Oct 18 [cited 2023 May 16];6(1):1–10. Available from:
411 <https://bmcpublichealth.biomedcentral.com/articles/10.1186/1471-2458-6-255>
- 412 19. Pellegrino R, Viegi G, Brusasco V, Crapo RO, Burgos F, Casaburi R, et al. Interpretative
413 strategies for lung function tests. *European Respiratory Journal*. 2005 Nov;26(5):948–68.
- 414 20. Kuster SP, Kuster D, Schindler C, Rochat MK, Braun J, Held L, et al. Reference equations
415 for lung function screening of healthy never-smoking adults aged 18–80 years. *European*
416 *Respiratory Journal* [Internet]. 2008 Apr 1 [cited 2023 May 16];31(4):860–8. Available
417 from: <https://erj.ersjournals.com/content/31/4/860>
- 418 21. Momtazmanesh S, Moghaddam SS, Ghamari SH, Rad EM, Rezaei N, Shobeiri P, et al.
419 Global burden of chronic respiratory diseases and risk factors, 1990–2019: an update
420 from the Global Burden of Disease Study 2019. *EClinicalMedicine* [Internet]. 2023

- 421 May;59:101936. Available from:
422 <https://linkinghub.elsevier.com/retrieve/pii/S258953702300113X>
- 423 22. Li H, Liang H, Wei L, Shi D, Su X, Li F, et al. Health Inequality in the Global Burden of
424 Chronic Obstructive Pulmonary Disease: Findings from the Global Burden of Disease
425 Study 2019. *International Journal of COPD*. 2022;17:1695–702.
- 426 23. Agustí A, Noell G, Brugada J, Faner R. Lung function in early adulthood and health in later
427 life: a transgenerational cohort analysis. *Lancet Respir Med*. 2017 Dec 1;5(12):935–45.
- 428 24. Duong ML, Usman A, Ma J, Xie Y, Huang J, Zaman M, et al. Associations between lung
429 function and physical and cognitive health in the Canadian Longitudinal Study on Aging
430 (CLSA): A cross-sectional study from a multicenter national cohort. *PLoS Med*. 2022 Feb
431 1;19(2).
- 432 25. Haynes JM. Pulmonary function test quality in the elderly: A comparison with younger
433 adults. *Respir Care*. 2014 Jan 1;59(1):16–21.
- 434 26. Czajkowska-Malinowska M, Tomalak W, Radliński J. Quality of Spirometry in the Elderly.
435 *Pneumonol Alergol Pol*. 2013 Oct 21;81(6):511–7.
- 436 27. Degryse J, Buffels J, Van Dijck Y, Decramer M, Nemery B. Accuracy of office spirometry
437 performed by trained primary-care physicians using the MIR spirometry hand-held
438 spirometer. *Respiration*. 2012 Jun;83(6):543–52.
- 439 28. Enright PL, Skloot GS, Cox-Ganser JM, Udasin IG, Herbert R. Quality of Spirometry
440 Performed by 13,599 Participants in the World Trade Center Worker and Volunteer
441 Medical Screening Program. *Respir Care*. 2010;55(3):303–9.
- 442